

onefit.ai: Helping people buy the right shoes online without compromising privacy

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Topic overview

This case study explores how [onefit.ai](#), an AI-driven startup, is tackling one of the most persistent challenges in online retail: helping people buy shoes that actually fit when they arrive on the doorstep. By using computer vision and machine learning techniques to estimate foot measurements from a single photograph, onefit.ai aims to reduce unnecessary returns, improve customer confidence, and lower the environmental impact associated with online footwear shopping. Taking part in The Alan Turing Institute's Turing Way Practitioners Hub has helped onefit.ai achieve its commitment of embedding responsible AI practices from the outset – particularly around data minimisation, privacy and user trust.

The trouble with buying shoes online

Buying footwear online is a frustrating experience for many people. Sizes vary widely between brands and regions, and even within brands themselves. For consumers, this often leads to uncertainty and a reliance on ordering multiple sizes 'just in case'. For retailers, it results in high return rates, increased logistics costs, and unnecessary waste. And while AI has been adopted for a range of purposes across the online retail sector, finding the perfect sizing and fit for everyone has remained tricky to solve

Onefit.ai founder Hinesh Mandalia saw how poorly the current system works for both shoppers and businesses, and how little had changed despite advances in e-commerce. Hinesh knew that any AI-based solution to this problem would need to balance technical accuracy and usability with robust transparency and privacy measures. Onefit.ai's approach reflects that

philosophy, combining advanced techniques with careful design choices about how data is collected and shared.

“This technology wouldn’t need to exist if we had an international standard for shoe sizing,” says Hinesh. “But there is no standard, which is why the issues of product returns and waste are so significant, and why we are trying to help tackle them with technology.”

The costs of poor fit and the challenge of trust

The scale of the problem onefit.ai is addressing is significant. Industry data suggests that [around one in five pairs of shoes bought online are returned](#) – significantly higher than the rate of 5% for in-store purchases. Beyond the direct financial costs for retailers (and the effect on their profit margins), these returns carry an environmental impact through additional shipping, handling and, in some cases, disposal. One study estimates that [22 billion pairs of shoes go to landfill each year](#).

At the same time, many consumers – possibly as many as 10% – [choose not to complete a purchase because they lack confidence that the shoes will fit](#). This affects conversion rates and disproportionately penalises people who cannot easily visit physical shops, including older customers and those with specific foot health needs such as flat feet or diabetic neuropathy.

Cutting-edge technology for more accurate sizing

Onefit.ai’s solution is designed to be simple from a user’s perspective. Customers take a photograph of their foot placed on a standard A4 sheet of white paper, which provides a reference scale. From this image, onefit.ai’s system estimates key foot dimensions and matches them against shoe-specific sizing data provided by retailers.

The system uses computer vision and machine learning techniques to isolate the foot from the background and extract measurements. Early versions relied on outline-matching approaches, but these were later replaced with a more advanced segmentation model to handle variations in potentially confounding factors such as lighting, positioning, unusual foot proportions, and even the pattern of a customer’s socks.

To address these factors and improve the accuracy of its model, onefit.ai invested heavily in training data. As well as collecting real examples, the team generated synthetic variations of foot measurements. Care was also taken to mitigate performance issues across different skin tones by adjusting how the system handles contrast.

Onefit.ai is already seeing encouraging signs from its pilot implementations with retailers, including the specialist company Wide Fit Shoes. Hinesh notes that while the evidence base is still limited, early data shows that around a third of users who complete the scanning process go on to make a purchase, and that returns are thus far very low. Partner retailers have reported a 2% uplift in overall sales, and a 3.5% increase in average order value.

Responsible AI: data privacy, user experience and sustainability

Perhaps the most important non-technical design decision was to minimise data collection. Onefit.ai does not collect personally identifying information alongside the foot images – nor does it require users to create accounts or submit email addresses to receive results. Foot images are used for model improvement but are not shared or sold, and data is retained only for as long as is necessary. Hinesh explains that this ethical restraint was crucial to increasing user confidence in the product, even though collecting additional data might have improved the model's accuracy. His preparatory work in this area included liaising with the British Standards Institute to discuss certifying onefit.ai's approach to the responsible use of data in an AI context.

User experience considerations also played a significant role: rather than assuming users would intuitively know how to position their feet, onefit.ai worked with a UX designer to test and refine the instructions provided to customers with the aim of finding an acceptable balance between necessary detail and simplicity of use. Terms and conditions, meanwhile, are written to be transparent and accessible.

On the environmental side, onefit.ai's models are trained using high-powered GPUs but run quickly and efficiently on lower-cost hardware once deployed, meaning they do not require heavy computing resources in day-to-day use. In the context of UN Sustainable Development Goals relating to climate action and responsible consumption and production (SDGs 12 and 13), Hinesh is also exploring ways of quantifying the benefits of reduced product returns. While a decrease in returns clearly implies lower emissions and waste, gathering consistent, high-quality data from across the retail and distribution supply chain is a complex and resource-intensive task.

Additionally, [trust in AI-powered shopping tools](#) remains a work in progress. Hinesh describes encountering scepticism from both consumers and retailers, with concerns ranging from data privacy to the accuracy of the technology. He notes that retailers tend to have particularly high expectations of AI systems' accuracy, and often lack the time or in-house expertise to evaluate potential new AI tools – an obstacle for startups seeking attention and trial opportunities. For this reason, says Hinesh, client onboarding has been an even bigger challenge than getting the technical aspects right.

On the consumer side, questions from potential users such as “What will you do with the pictures of my feet?” and “Will my data be sold?” reflect an understandable wariness and have played a significant role in shaping OneFit's data handling and ethical decisions.

Next steps: Expanding the OneFit evidence base

Onefit.ai's immediate focus is on building a stronger evidence base around its system. This includes further pilot deployments with retailers, collecting more end-to-end data on returns and purchasing behaviour, and working towards more robust measurement of environmental impact.

From a technical perspective, the team plans to continue refining the system's accuracy across edge cases such as suboptimal lighting conditions and unusual foot placements. There is also interest in exploring more advanced computer vision techniques, such as single-shot 3D reconstruction from 2D images – although Hinesh emphasises that any such addition must be balanced against compute cost and practical benefit.

A longer-term ambition is to explore whether similar AI-based approaches could be applied to other categories of clothing purchased online.

Reflections on The Turing Way Practitioners Hub

“Taking part in the Practitioners Hub made me realise that the challenges I was facing weren't just a 'me' problem. Data privacy, user trust and AI scepticism kept coming up in conversations with others, even though we were working in completely different domains. Sessions like the AI challenges workshop really helped me question my assumptions and gave me a practical framework for thinking about AI risks and responsibilities. It also helped me develop a more empathetic approach to communicating the benefits and limitations of our system with potential clients in retail, many of whom are AI-hesitant and inexperienced. The Practitioners Hub has given me confidence to keep going and to be more open in how I engage with customers and other people building AI responsibly.”

Hinesh Mandalia, Founder of onefit.ai

Key takeaways

- Poor fit remains a major barrier to effective online footwear retail, driving up product returns, waste and lost sales.
- AI-based technology can improve sizing accuracy and sales – but only if retailers are persuaded to adopt and users trust how their private data is being handled.
- Responsible AI practices such as data minimisation and transparency are a key consideration in consumer-facing applications.
- Representatives of retail companies may be sceptical of AI or lack knowledge of the technology – and this needs to be treated with empathy and not misinterpreted as hostility.
- Building an evidence base around the effectiveness of an AI system, as well as aspects such as its environmental impact, is important but not always straightforward.
- The Turing Way Practitioners Hub provided reassurance, peer learning and practical tools for navigating shared AI challenges.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under [The Turing Way Practitioners Hub](#) 2025-26 Cohort - case study series. The Practitioners Hub is [The Turing Way](#) project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Hinesh Mandalia from Hin Man Technology Ltd**, as an Expert-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025-26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher - Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager. **Arielle Bennett** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

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